

A model for the origin of planetary water. Solar reduction of silicon dioxide.

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1. Provisions of the second edition of logical research.

We eliminate secondary entities (the water cycle) as particular manifestations of the concept under study. Therefore, we focus on the "geocosmic synthesis of water, a method for reducing silicon dioxide." In practice, this means the emergence of the world ocean.

A logical reconstruction of planet Earth in the pre-oceanic era. The atmosphere as we know it today was absent and looked more like a dust cloud. A number of studies [3a; 3b; 3c] strongly suggest a cloud of nanostructured, web-like silicon dioxide with a huge catalytic surface area. This ensures the most efficient reaction of the nanomaterial with the solar wind. After the reaction, the synthesized water was trapped and condensed within the nanostructure, and along with it, it precipitated from the outer regions of the silicon cloud under the force of gravity. This subsequently formed the world's oceans and atmosphere.

2. Pre-oceanic Earth, Hadean Eon (Hadean).

- Rocky geological relief.
- Extremely high volcanic activity.
- The near-Earth atmosphere is oversaturated with finely dispersed volcanic silicate dust in aerosol form.

2. Reduction reaction of silicon dioxide by solar wind

The reaction formula is:

3. Result – formation of the hydrosphere

Reasons:

- The fundamental possibility of water synthesis from silicate matter under ion irradiation is confirmed by the analysis of cosmic regolith [1].
- Isotopic mismatch of external sources. The isotopic composition of cometary matter (D/H ratio) significantly exceeds the values of the Earth's oceans, which excludes cometary water as the main source of the formation of the hydrosphere [2].

SOURCES

1. Nature Geoscience (2023). A solar wind-derived water reservoir on the Moon hosted by impact glass beads.
DOI: 10.1038/s41561-023-01159-6
2. Science (2014). 67P/ Churyumov-Gerasimenko, a Jupiter-family comet with a high D/H ratio.
DOI: 10.1126/science.1261952
3. **3a.** An experimental investigation of the condensation of silicate grains.
DOI: 10.1086/182689
3b. Schmid et al. (2024): Volcanic Eruption in the Nanoworld: Efficient Oxygen Exchange at the Si/SnO₂ Interface.
DOI: 10.1002/sml.202404508
3c. Physical Review Letters (2000): Growth and Form of Cosmic Dust Aggregates.
DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.85.2426

Figure 1: Model of atmospheric formation of planetary water.

Figure 2: Prooceanic Earth, Hadean Eon. Reconstruction.